

ON THE DIVISIBILITY OF $a^n \pm b^n$ BY POWERS OF n

Salvatore Tringali¹

*Laboratoire Jacques-Louis Lions (LJLL), Université Pierre et Marie Curie
(UPMC), Paris, France*

tringali@ann.jussieu.fr

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Abstract

We determine all triples (a, b, n) of positive integers such that a and b are relatively prime and n^k divides $a^n + b^n$ (respectively, $a^n - b^n$), when k is the maximum of a and b (in fact, we answer a slightly more general question). As a by-product, we see that, for $m, n \in \mathbb{N}^+$ with $n \geq 2$, n^m divides $m^n + 1$ if and only if $(m, n) = (2, 3)$ or $(1, 2)$, which generalizes problems from the 1990 and 1999 editions of the International Mathematical Olympiad. The results are related to a conjecture by K. Györy and C. Smyth on the finiteness of the sets $R_k^\pm(a, b) := \{n \in \mathbb{N}^+ : n^k \mid (a^n \pm b^n)\}$, where a, b, k are fixed integers with $k \geq 3$, $\gcd(a, b) = 1$ and $|ab| \geq 2$; in particular, we find that the conjecture is true for $k \geq \max(|a|, |b|)$.

1. Introduction

It is a problem from the 1990 edition of the International Mathematical Olympiad (shortly, IMO) to find all integers $n \geq 2$ such that $n^2 \mid (2^n + 1)$. This appears as Problem 7.1.15 (p. 147) in [1], together with a solution by the authors (p. 323), who show that the only possible n is 3. On the other hand, Problem 4 in the 1999 IMO asks for all pairs (n, p) of positive integers such that p is a (positive rational) prime, $n \leq 2p$ and $n^{p-1} \mid ((p-1)^n + 1)$. This is Problem 5.1.3 (p. 105) in the same book as above, whose solution by the authors (p. 105) is concluded with the remark that “With a little bit more work, we can even erase the condition $n \leq 2p$.” Specifically, it is found that the required pairs are $(1, p)$, $(2, 2)$ and $(3, 3)$, where p is an arbitrary prime.

It is now fairly natural to ask whether similar conclusions can be drawn in relation to the more general problem of determining all pairs (m, n) of positive integers for which $n^m \mid (m^n + 1)$. In fact, the question is answered in the positive, and even in

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a stronger form, by Theorem 1 below, where the following observations are taken into account to rule out from the analysis a few trivial cases: Given $a, b \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $n, k \in \mathbb{N}^+$, we have that $1^k \mid (a^n \pm b^n)$ and $n^k \mid (a^n - a^n)$. Furthermore, $n^k \mid (a^n \pm b^n)$ if and only if $n^k \mid (b^n \pm a^n)$, and also if and only if $n^k \mid ((-a)^n \pm (-b)^n)$. Finally, $n^k \mid (a^n + (-a)^n)$ for n odd and $n^k \mid (a^n - (-a)^n)$ for n even.

Theorem 1. *Let a, b and n be integers such that $n \geq 2$, $a \geq \max(1, |b|)$ and $b \geq 0$ for n even, and set $\delta := \gcd(a, b)$, $\alpha := \delta^{-1}a$ and $\beta := \delta^{-1}b$.*

- (1) *Assume that $\beta \neq -\alpha$ when n is odd. Then, $n^\alpha \mid (a^n + b^n)$ and $n^\alpha \mid (a^n + \beta^n)$ if and only if $(a, b, n) = (2, 1, 3)$ or $(2^c, 2^c, 2)$ for $c \in \{0, 1, 2\}$.*
- (2) *Let $\beta \neq \alpha$. Then, $n^\alpha \mid (a^n - b^n)$ and $n^\alpha \mid (a^n - \beta^n)$ if and only if $(a, b, n) = (3, 1, 2)$ or $(2, -1, 3)$.*

Theorem 1 will be proved in Section 2. In fact, our proof is just the result of a meticulous refinement of the solutions already known for the IMO problems mentioned in the preamble. Thus, our only possible merit, if any at all, has been that of bringing into focus a clearer picture of (some of) their essential features.

Some comments on Theorem 1 are in order before proceeding. First, it would be interesting to extend the theorem, possibly at the expense of some extra solutions, by removing the assumption that $n^\alpha \mid (a^n + \beta^n)$ or $n^\alpha \mid (a^n - \beta^n)$ (the notation is the same as in the statement of the result), but at present we do not have great ideas for this. Secondly, three out of the six triples obtained by the present formulation come from the identity $2^3 + 1^3 = 3^2$. Lastly, the result yields a solution of the problems which have originally stimulated this work, as we have the following corollary (of which we omit the obvious proof):

Corollary 2. *Let $m, n \in \mathbb{N}^+$. Then $n^m \mid (m^n + 1)$ if and only if either $(m, n) = (2, 3)$, $(m, n) = (1, 2)$, or $n = 1$ and m is arbitrary.*

For the notation and terminology used herein without definition, as well as for material concerning classical topics in number theory, the reader should refer to [5]. In particular, we write \mathbb{Z} for the integers, \mathbb{N} for the nonnegative integers, and \mathbb{N}^+ for $\mathbb{N} \setminus \{0\}$, each of these sets being endowed with its ordinary addition $+$, multiplication \cdot and total order \leq (as is customary, \geq will stand for the dual order of \leq). For $a, b \in \mathbb{Z}$ with $a^2 + b^2 \neq 0$, we denote by $\gcd(a, b)$ the greatest common divisor of a and b . Lastly, we let \mathbb{P} be the set of all (positive rational) primes and, for $c \in \mathbb{Z} \setminus \{0\}$ and $p \in \mathbb{P}$, we use $e_p(c)$ for the greatest exponent $k \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $p^k \mid c$, which is extended to \mathbb{Z} by $e_p(0) := \infty$.

We will make use at some point of the following lemma, which belongs to the folklore and is typically attributed to É. Lucas [6] and R. D. Carmichael [3] (the latter having fixed an error in Lucas' original work in the 2-adic case).

Lemma 3 (Lifting-the-exponent lemma). *For all $x, y \in \mathbb{Z}$, $\ell \in \mathbb{N}^+$ and $p \in \mathbb{P}$ such that $p \nmid xy$ and $p \mid (x - y)$, the following conditions are satisfied:*

- (1) *If $p \geq 3$, ℓ is odd, or $4 \mid (x - y)$, then $e_p(x^\ell - y^\ell) = e_p(x - y) + e_p(\ell)$.*
- (2) *If $p = 2$, ℓ is even and $e_2(x - y) = 1$, then $e_2(x^\ell - y^\ell) = e_2(x + y) + e_2(\ell)$.*

The study of the congruences $a^n \pm b^n \equiv 0 \pmod{n^k}$ has a very long history, dating back at least to Euler, who proved that, for all relatively prime integers a, b with $a > b \geq 1$, every primitive prime divisor of $a^n - b^n$ is congruent to 1 modulo n ; see [2, Theorem I] for a proof and [2, §1] for the terminology. However, since there are so many results related to the question, instead of trying to summarize them here, we just refer the interested reader to the paper [4], whose authors provide a thorough account of the existing literature on the topic and characterize, for $a, b \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $k \in \mathbb{N}^+$, the set $R_k^+(a, b)$, respectively $R_k^-(a, b)$, of all positive integers n such that n^k divides $a^n + b^n$, respectively $a^n - b^n$ (note that no assumption is made about the coprimality of a and b), while addressing the problem of finding the exceptional cases when $R_1^-(a, b)$ and $R_2^-(a, b)$ are finite; see, in particular, [4, Theorems 1–2 and 18]. Nonetheless, the related question of determining, given $a, b \in \mathbb{Z}$ with $\gcd(a, b) = 1$, all positive integers n such that n^k divides $a^n + b^n$ (respectively, $a^n - b^n$), when k is the maximum of $|a|$ and $|b|$, does not appear to be considered in either [4] or the references therein.

On another hand, it is suggested in [4] that $R_k^+(a, b)$ and $R_k^-(a, b)$ are both finite provided that a, b and k are fixed integers with $k \geq 3$, $\gcd(a, b) = 1$ and $|ab| \geq 2$ (the authors point out that the question is probably a difficult one, even assuming the ABC conjecture). Although far from being an answer to this, Theorem 1 in the present paper implies that, under the same assumptions as above, $R_k^+(a, b)$ and $R_k^-(a, b)$ are finite for $k \geq \max(|a|, |b|)$.

2. Proofs

First, for the sake of exposition, we give a couple of lemmas.

Lemma 4. *Let $x, y, z \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $\ell \in \mathbb{N}^+$ such that $\gcd(x, y) = 1$ and $z \mid (x^\ell + y^\ell)$. Then xy and z are relatively prime, $q \nmid (x^\ell - y^\ell)$ for every integer $q \geq 3$ for which $q \mid z$, and $4 \nmid z$ provided that ℓ is even. Moreover, if there exists an odd prime divisor p of both z and ℓ such that $\gcd(\ell, p - 1) = 1$, then $p \mid (x + y)$, ℓ is odd and $e_p(z) \leq e_p(x + y) + e_p(\ell)$.*

Proof. The first part is routine (we omit the details). As for the second, let p be an odd prime dividing both z and ℓ with $\gcd(\ell, p - 1) = 1$. Also, considering that z and xy are relatively prime (by the above), denote by y^{-1} an inverse of y modulo p and by

ω the order of xy^{-1} modulo p , viz the smallest $k \in \mathbb{N}^+$ such that $(xy^{-1})^k \equiv 1 \pmod p$; cf. [5, §6.8]. Since $(xy^{-1})^{2\ell} \equiv 1 \pmod p$, we have $\omega \mid 2\ell$. It follows from Fermat's little theorem and [5, Theorem 88] that ω divides $\gcd(2\ell, p - 1)$, whence we get $\omega \mid 2$, using that $\gcd(\ell, p - 1) = 1$. This in turn implies that $p \mid (x^2 - y^2)$, so that either $p \mid (x - y)$ or $p \mid (x + y)$. But $p \mid (x - y)$ would give that $p \mid (x^\ell - y^\ell)$, which is impossible by the first part of the claim (since $p \geq 3$). So $p \mid (x + y)$, with the result that ℓ is odd: For, if $2 \mid \ell$, then $p \mid 2x^\ell$ (because $p \mid z \mid (x^\ell + y^\ell)$ and $y \equiv -x \pmod p$), which would lead to $\gcd(x, y) \geq p$ (again, using that p is odd), and thus to a contradiction. The rest is an immediate application of Lemma 3. \square

Lemma 5. *Let $x, y, z \in \mathbb{Z}$ such that x, y are odd and $x, y \geq 0$. Then $x^2 - y^2 = 2^z$ if and only if $z \geq 3$, $x = 2^{z-2} + 1$ and $y = 2^{z-2} - 1$.*

Proof. Since x and y are odd, $x^2 - y^2$ is divisible by 8, namely $z \geq 3$, and there exist $i, j \in \mathbb{N}^+$ such that $i + j = z$, $x - y = 2^i$ and $x + y = 2^j$. It follows that $x = 2^{j-1} + 2^{i-1}$ and $y = 2^{j-1} - 2^{i-1}$, and then $j > i$ and $i = 1$ (otherwise x and y would be even). The rest is straightforward. \square

Now, we are ready to write down the proof of the main result.

Proof of Theorem 1. Point (1): Assume that $n^\alpha \mid (a^n + b^n)$, $n^\alpha \mid (\alpha^n + \beta^n)$, and $\beta \neq -\alpha$ when n is odd. Since α and β are coprime (by construction), it holds that $\beta \neq 0$, for otherwise $n \mid (\alpha^n + \beta^n)$ and $n \geq 2$ would give $\gcd(\alpha, \beta) \geq 2$. Also, $\alpha = |\beta|$ if and only if $\alpha = \beta = 1$ and $n = 2$ (as $\beta \geq 0$ for n even), hence 2^δ divides $2\delta^2$, which is possible if and only if $\delta \in \{1, 2, 4\}$ and gives $(a, b, n) = (1, 1, 2)$, $(2, 2, 2)$, or $(4, 4, 2)$. So, we are left with the case when

$$\alpha \geq 2 \quad \text{and} \quad \alpha > |\beta| \geq 1, \tag{1}$$

since $\alpha \geq \max(1, |\beta|)$. Considering that $4 \mid n^2$ for n even, it follows from Lemma 4 that n is odd and $\gcd(\alpha\beta, n) = 1$. Denote by p the smallest prime divisor of n . Again by Lemma 4, it is then found that p divides $\alpha + \beta$ and

$$\alpha - 1 \leq (\alpha - 1) \cdot e_p(n) \leq e_p(\alpha + \beta). \tag{2}$$

Furthermore, $\alpha + \beta \geq 1$ by equation (1), so that

$$\alpha + \beta = p^r s, \quad \text{with } r, s \in \mathbb{N}^+ \text{ and } p \nmid s. \tag{3}$$

Therefore, equations (1) and (3) yield that $2\alpha \geq p^r s + 1$. This implies by equation (2), since $r = e_p(\alpha + \beta)$, that $3^r s \leq p^r s \leq 2r + 1$, which is possible only if $p = 3$ and $r = s = 1$. Thus, by equations (2) and (3), we get $\alpha + \beta = 3$ and $\alpha = 2$, namely $(\alpha, \beta) = (2, 1)$. Also, $e_3(n) = 1$, and hence $n = 3t$ for some $t \in \mathbb{N}^+$ with $\gcd(6, t) = 1$. It follows that $t^2 \mid (\gamma^t + 1)$ for $\gamma = 2^3$.

So suppose, for the sake of contradiction, that $t \geq 2$ and let q be the least prime divisor of t . Then, another application of Lemma 4 gives $2e_q(t) \leq e_q(\gamma + 1) + e_q(t)$, and accordingly $1 \leq e_q(t) \leq e_q(\gamma + 1) = e_q(3^2)$, which is however absurd, due to the fact that $\gcd(3, t) = 1$. Hence $t = 1$, i.e., $n = 3$, and putting everything together we obtain the claim, because $2^3 + 1^3 = 3^2$ and $3^{2\delta}$ divides $\delta^2 \cdot (2^3 + 1^3)$ only if $\delta = 1$.

Point (2). Assume that $n^\alpha \mid (a^n - b^n)$, $n^\alpha \mid (\alpha^n - \beta^n)$, and $\beta \neq \alpha$. Since $\gcd(\alpha, \beta) = 1$, we get as in the proof of point (1) that $\beta \neq 0$, while $\alpha = |\beta|$ only if $\alpha = 1$, $\beta = -1$, and n is odd (again, $\beta \geq 0$ for n even), which is however impossible, because it would give that $n \mid 2$ with $n \geq 3$. So, we can suppose from now on that α and β satisfy the same conditions as in equation (1), and write n as $2^r s$, where $r \in \mathbb{N}$, $s \in \mathbb{N}^+$ and $\gcd(2, s) = 1$. We have the following:

Case 1: $r = 0$, i.e., $n = s$. Then, n is odd, and hence $n^\alpha \mid (a^n + (-b)^n)$ and $n^\alpha \mid (\alpha^n + (-\beta)^n)$, so by point (1) we get $(a, b, n) = (2, -1, 3)$.

Case 2: $r \geq 1$. Since n is even and $\gcd(\alpha, \beta) = 1$, both α and β are odd, that is $8 \mid (\alpha^2 - \beta^2)$. It follows from point (1) of Lemma 3 that

$$e_2(\alpha^n - \beta^n) = e_2(\alpha^2 - \beta^2) + e_2(2^{r-1}s) = e_2(\alpha^2 - \beta^2) + r - 1. \tag{4}$$

(With the notation there, we apply the lemma with $x = \alpha^2$, $y = \beta^2$, $\ell = 2^{r-1}s$, and $p = 2$.) Also, $2^{r\alpha} \mid (\alpha^n - \beta^n)$, so equation (4) yields

$$(\alpha - 1) \cdot r \leq e_2(\alpha^2 - \beta^2) - 1. \tag{5}$$

There now exist $u, v \in \mathbb{N}^+$ with $u \geq 2$ and $\gcd(2, v) = 1$ such that $\alpha^2 - \beta^2 = 2^{u+1}v$, with the result that $\alpha > 2^{u/2}\sqrt{v}$. Hence, taking also into account that $2^x \geq x + 1$ for every $x \in \mathbb{R}$ with $x \geq 1$, we get by equation (5) that

$$\left(\frac{u}{2} + 1\right) \sqrt{v} \leq 2^{u/2}\sqrt{v} < \frac{u}{r} + 1, \tag{6}$$

which is possible only if $r = 1$ and $\sqrt{v} < 2$. Then $2^{u/2}\sqrt{v} < u + 1$, in such a way that $2 \leq u \leq 5$ and $v = 1$ (using that v is odd). In consequence of Lemma 5, all of this implies, at the end of the day, that $\alpha = 2^z + 1$, $\beta = 2^z - 1$ and $n = 2s$ (recall that we want the conditions in equation (1) to be satisfied and $\beta \geq 0$ for n even), where z is an integer between 1 and 4. But we need $2^z \leq z + 1$ by equation (5), so necessarily $z = 1$, i.e., $\alpha = 3$ and $\beta = 1$. Finally, we check that $(2s)^3 \mid (3^{2s} - 1^{2s})$ if and only if $s = 1$: For, if $s \geq 2$ and q is the smallest prime divisor of s , then $0 < 3e_q(s) \leq e_q(3^2 - 1)$ by Lemma 4, which is absurd since $\gcd(2, s) = 1$. This gives $(a, b, n) = (3, 1, 2)$, while it is trivially seen that $2^{3\delta}$ divides $\delta^2 \cdot (3^2 - 1^2)$ if and only if $\delta = 1$.

Putting all the pieces together, the proof is thus complete. □

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